

The effect of Cognitive behavioral therapy on the Internet in reducing Anxiety caused by the emerging COVID-19 virus in Taif Governorate

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 30, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 31, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, Anxiety Caused By The Emerging Covid-19 Virus</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4651489</p>	<p><i>Anxiety disorders are highly prevalent spread of the spread the Corona virus, and has no treatment yet. It has been suggested that Internet-based cognitive behavioral therapy (ICBT) increases the opportunity to communicate with patients, and saves costs. Objective: The study evaluated the efficacy of an Internet-based cognitive behavioral therapy (ICBT) in Reducing the level of anxiety caused by the Corona virus. Method: Fifty-four patients with COVID-19 anxiety disorders according to DSM-IV, (25 males – 29 females), were randomly divided into two groups (28 experimental - 26 control), Participants in the experimental group received a (14) cognitive behavioral therapy (ICBT) sessions in seven - weeks. Outcomes were evaluated post-treatment between experimental and control, males and female in the experimental groups. Results: using the independent sample t-test, there was no significant difference between the experimental group and control group, males and female in the experimental groups before intervention, the level of COVID-19 anxiety among participants in the pilot group decreased compared to the control group following the intervention, and there was no difference in the level of COVID-19 anxiety between males and females in the experimental groups after intervention. Conclusion: Results of the study provide support for the efficacy of ICBT for Reducing Anxiety from the Corona virus.</i></p>

Introduction

The first case in January 2020 In China and it the number of cases began to increase at the time of writing this study, more than 126 million casualties and 2.76million deaths due to (COVID-19) have been reported. (World Health Organization)

The literature on COVID-19 offers a wide range of harmful psychological effects of its spread. The proliferation of information on COVID-19 such as the rapid spread of infection among humans, especially among people with HIV, the elderly, and those with chronic diseases, has led to widespread anxiety among members of society. (Kim and Su, 2020). The rapid spread of COVID-19 has led states to follow quarantine, isolation and curfews in cities and travel to and from countries, causing many people to be anxious, stressed and depressed (Brooks, et al., 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the level of general anxiety increased by 35.1%, the level of sleep quality by 18.2%, and the level of depression by 20.1% (Huang and Zhao, 2020). Anxiety causes harmful effects such as lack of adjustment to the surroundings, low school level, production and work rates, and may cause a desire to commit suicide (Uludag, 2014). Media interest in showing the prevalence of epidemic diseases and mortality rates, while ignoring the psychological and mental problems that coincide with their appearance leads to the spread of anxiety disorder (Tucci, 2017). The World Health Organization (WHO) has reported that people's exposure to a high level of anxiety causes them to become immune-deficient, increasing the risk of contracting (Moghanibashi-Mansourieh, 2020).

During epidemics, the media and social networking sites on the Internet may resort to broadcasting reports in emotional language to attract attention, which contributes to spreading fear among people and contribute to panic buying (Garfin et al., 2020). Social media can be used to provide psychosocial support to reduce anxiety (Seabrook et al. 2016). A psychologist can use CBT to reduce the level of mental disorders through e-mail, phone calls, or automated reminders (Andersson, 2016). Cognitive behavioral therapy can be used to correct negative thoughts and irrational beliefs, and to transform them into beliefs accompanied by emotional and behavioral control (Auf, 2018). Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is characterized by the use of techniques such as the ability to persuade and seeks to reveal negative thoughts and irrational beliefs, and the patient examines what he reminds himself of, adjusts and replaces the correct idea (Salama, 2006).

There are many benefits to cognitive behavioral therapy through the Internet that it helps a patient to communicate with the therapist at any time and place, and the therapist can communicate for unlimited periods with the patient (Ye, et al., 2015). The Group Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy had decreased Anxiety and Depression in Nigerian Breast Cancer Patients (Onyedibe, et al., 2020). Internet-based cognitive behavioral

therapy program Lower the level anxiety disorders for adolescents and Treatment gains were maintained at 3- and 12-month follow-up (Stjerneklar, et al. ,2019).Hence the need to test the effectiveness of Cognitive behavioral therapy in the management of psychological distress such as the anxiety caused by the spread of the Corona virus. The objective of this study is therefore to investigate whether group CBT will be effective in the management of the anxiety caused by the spread of the Corona virus.

2. Methods

2.1 Participants

This study was conducted with (54) patients with anxiety spread of corona virus (25 males – 29 females). Their diagnoses were determined based on Corona virus Anxiety Scale (prepared by researchers), after agreement of ethics committee at Taif University and patients. Sample selection conditions were: 1) gets a score in the Higher quarters of the anxiety spread of the corona virus scale; 2) Can handle social media like Twitter and Zoom. The exclusion criteria for the study were taking any anxiolytic medications thus confound the results. Participants' age ranged from 20 to 54 years, with a mean age of 39.4 (SD = 13.6). The study sample was randomly assigned and they were divided into two groups:experimental group and control group. Table 1 shows the demographic variables of the sample.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the sample

Variable	Category	sex		Total
		Male	Females	
Age	20-40	12	13	25
	40-60	13	16	29
	Total	25	29	54
Social Status	Single	8	12	20
	Married	17	17	34
	Total	25	29	54
Educational attainment	Student	10	10	20
	graduate	15	19	34
	Total	25	29	54
group	experimental	13	15	28
	control	12	14	26
	Total	25	29	54

2.2 Measures

COVID-19 Anxiety Scale

We did not find scale in the literature to assess the levels of Anxiety caused by the emerging COVID-19, Therefore it was developed a scale, correspond to the specific phobia diagnosis criteria of the (300.29) DSM-IV-TR Criteria.

Anxiety spread of corona virus were measured using the 32-item self-report inventory. the items are answered on a 5-point Likert type items ranging from "0= strongly disagree" to "4= strongly agree", with a higher score indicating a more anxiety spread of corona virus, that for anxiety scores of (0-42) shows Mild anxiety, (43- 85) shows Moderate anxiety while scores between (86-128) indicate Severe anxiety and its reliability and validity have been established, the Cronbach's reliability coefficients met the criterion for acceptable reliability (> 0.60), The Cronbach alpha coefficient for the scale was 0.71.

2.3 Intervention

The treatment was a combined online CBT program, the program was reviewed by three professors specializing in psychological guidance panel of three CBT experts in Taifuniversity, Researchers and patients agreed upon the time and dates of session ICBT each week, where (14) sessions were delivered through an Internet and received two sessions weekly, Each session (90) minutes Through Zoom program, a 10-minute break in the middle of the session. The first session included introductory information about the program ICBT, and how the all sessions were done. The rest of the sessions included discussion and dialogue on causes of concern, texts and videos about how to prevent COVID-19, negative automatic thoughts, identifying stimuli that promote anxiety caused by the emerging COVID-19 virus and methods to modify that anxiety including finding ways to manage stimuli. Participants were directed to interaction, discussion and dialogue during the sessions and read texts, watch videos and to complete homework assignments, the guidance supportive phone calls included observation and post-session feedback. Group were assessed at baseline before intervention, immediately after the intervention (post-test), Table 2. A summary of sessions Cognitive behavioral therapy.

Table 2. Contents of the sessions for 7-week Group Cognitive behavioral Therapy.

Sessions	Contents of the Sessions	Homework
Session 1	- Acquaintance between the therapists and the participants	Write down the information you know about the Corona virus

- General introduction to CBT		
Session 2	Cognitive reconstruction through training. Identifying negative irrational thoughts and uncovering contradictions, evidence and proofs	Writing irrational thoughts about the Corona virus
Session 3	Muscle relaxation training	Relax morning and evening and any time you feel anxious
Session 4	Reframe the problem of anxiety over the spread of Corona	Write any information mentioned during the session, and write down the main causes of the problem.
Session 5	Training in protection against anxiety, identification of stress, its effects and its concept, training on a skill set to get rid of stress, how to apply in real life	Writing techniques for facing stress in real situations
Session 6	Control negative thoughts and wrong thinking	Write down negative thoughts that cause anxiety about the Corona virus, and what are controlling you
Session 7	Optimism training in stressful situations	Read the prevention brochure more than twice a day, and do a physical activity
Session 8	Visualization training for corona virus anxiety	Write down the advice that you give yourself and others to encourage them not to worry
Session 9	Cognitive relaxation	Write the idea that caused you anxiety and turn attention and imagine the attitudes of the individual
Session 10	Training to change passive self-talk to positive self-talk	Write negative talk and then repeat modified phrases for wrong ideas ten times
Session 11	Self-monitoring training	Write the idea that caused you anxiety and the action that was done to drive the idea away and its success rate.
Session 12	Immunization against anxiety (awareness and understanding phase- information acquisition phase - skills application and follow-up)	Identify worrying situations and apply the three stages to deal with them
Session 13	Cognitive reconstruction (logical justification - identifying negative ideas - turning negative thoughts into positive - self-promotion)	Writing a negative attitude and the positive idea that he replaced it - how to strengthen oneself
Session 14	How to prevent the Corona virus	Writing negative automatic thoughts

2.4 Statistical analyses

Mean pretest-posttest and standard deviation change in Corona virus Anxiety Scale measures within individuals were calculated between experimental group and control group after immediate using t-test, comparisons between (males – females) after immediate using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test, given the small sample size.

3. Results

The Independent T-test was used to check for significant differences between the experimental and control groups, male and female in anxiety level by the emerging COVID-19 virus before intervention, all comparisons yielded no significant differences in between the experimental group (M= 96.0, SD= 3.8) and control group (M= 96.2, SD= 2.9), Female (M=96.7, SD= 2.8) and Male (M=96.3, SD= 3.9). data are summarized in Table 3.

Table. 3: Comparison of the mean between the experimental group and control group, Female and Male before the intervention and after intervention between experimental and control group

	group	N	Mean	(SD)	t-test	
					t	Sig
Before intervention	Experimental	28	96.0	3.8	2.85	P> .05
	Control	26	96.2	2.9		
Before intervention	Female	29	96.7	2.8	1.54	P> .05
	Male	25	96.3	3.9		
After intervention	Experimental	28	68.07	3.06	14.06	P< .05
	Control	26	93.61	9.07		

T-test was carried out to compare the Experimental group with the control group after intervention, comparison yielded had significant decrease in anxiety level caused by the emerging COVID-19 among participants in the Experimental group (M= 68.07, SD= 3.06) compared to the participants in control group (M= 93.61, SD= 9.07), data are summarized in Table 3.

Mann-Whitney U test was carried out to compare Female group with male group in the Experimental group after intervention, comparison yielded no significant differences in anxiety level caused by the emerging COVID-19, these comparisons was calculated in Table 5.

Table 4. Mann-Whitney U test result of the anxiety score of caused by the emerging COVID-19 virus after immediately between female and Male in the experimental group

group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank	U	Z	Sig
Female	15	13.00	195.00	75.0	1.05	P> .05
male	13	16.23	211.00			

4. Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to explore the effect of Cognitive behavioral therapy on the Internet in reducing anxiety caused by the emerging COVID-19 virus in Taif Governorate. The findings revealed that there is reducing the level of anxiety caused by the Corona virus after the online Cognitive behavioral therapy. This may be due in the current study to urging the testers to use daily relaxation to reduce stress, stress and mental stress, which contributed to reducing their negative effects, making them able to control them, and also urging them to describe the stressful attitudes that cause anxiety caused by the spread of Corona, irrational thoughts that preceded or followed emotion, and rewrote the idea that caused anxiety, but in a more rational way, which is known as cognitive reformulation. This finding is in line with previous research findings such as Onyedibe, et al. (2020) reducing the level of anxiety and depression in women with breast cancer was as a result of participating in the Cognitive behavioral therapy after intervention. Stefan et al. (2019) argument that Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy, and Acceptance and Commitment Therapy/ Acceptance-based behavioral therapy reduced the level of general anxiety. The result of the current study differs with Ólafsdóttir, et al. (2018) that anxiety level did not change significantly result Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy.

The researchers also studied the differences between males and females in the level of anxiety caused by COVID-19 virus after Cognitive behavioral therapy, the results found no differences between males and females in the experimental group. This is a sign that cognitive behavioral therapy directs mentors to manage unhealthy anxiety caused by this COVID-19 virus by providing them with alternative adaptive skills during sessions. This finding is in line with Sorour (2013) there are no significant statistical differences in the mean of the degree of the improvement resultant from application of behavior cognitive therapy among social phobia patients in accordance with sex. The result of the current research with Abbas (2015) there is statistically significant differences between males and females in the level of anxiety following cognitive behavioral therapy for males.

The study found some problems that faced cognitive-behavioral therapy through the Internet, which is the lack of visual communication between the therapist and the patient, which helps in obtaining accurate information about the level of anxiety about the Corona virus, and ensuring the implementation of the session procedures.

In conclusion, the results of this study showed that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on the Internet was successful in significantly reducing anxiety caused by the emerging COVID-19 virus among male and female. It underlines the importance of using psychotherapy as an alternative therapy in the treatment of anxiety Through medication, this would significantly Increases the quality of life.

5. Conclusions

According to the scores, obtained after the Corona virus Anxiety Scale, we can state that, Cognitive behavioral therapy can be relied upon to reduce the level of anxiety caused by the spread of corona virus and that women and men have responded to therapeutic intervention to relieve anxiety. Future research might investigate Positive self-talk strategies using qualitative and quantitative methods to enhance Reducing anxiety in the elderly.

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